

DETERMINANTS OF THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

Advances in information and technology have opened a new world order on the wheels of globalization. This development has led to an increase in trade both within the country and abroad, providing more flexible logical tools and methods with communication capabilities. This paper studies the determinants of the competitiveness of the textile industry in Uzbekistan using the cases of 4 enterprises

Keywords: competitiveness, textile industry, financial ratios, Uzbekistan

Introduction

What was considered impossible has now become a reality. Growing globalization, cheap but effective communication tools have opened the doors to international markets for domestic commercial firms, helping them to generate more and more profits. First, it needs to be made clear that competitiveness means achieving better results than anything else (Murths and Lenway, 1998). Lall (2001) also determined that the results were better than all direct competitors and indirect competitors (substitute suppliers) in all aspects, without exception, in order to provide large profits that gave a competitive advantage over others.

Lall (2001) explained that in order to avoid falling into the trap of competitiveness, it is recommended for simplicity to measure it in terms of firm profitability. Momaia and Selby (1998) further clarified that competition is not limited to the firm. It can be either a sector or a country. One side of the picture shows that because domestic for-profit firms have fewer opportunities and competitive potentials, they have now gained access to developed markets. For a correct assessment, it is necessary to consider the other side of this picture, which indicated that firms in developed markets were attracted towards underdeveloped markets in order to diversify risks and increase their client base. Firms in an underdeveloped market face this threat due to their inability to compete with developed market firms. Firms have reached the maximum customer base limit in a mature market due to intense competition. The lifting of the restriction proved to be more fruitful for international firms. This openness increased competition in an underdeveloped market as well, which made it necessary to re-examine the issue of competitiveness.

Determinants

Financial leverage.

Whenever it comes to the competitiveness of firms, the first thing that comes to mind is the sources of funds to achieve competitive advantage. This raises the question of how you can use funding sources to gain a competitive advantage.

The answer was given in the MM Hypothesis. Modigliani and Miller suggested that a firm's capital structure and profitability were irrelevant in ideal market conditions, for example, when there were no taxes, transaction costs, and investment opportunities (Modigliani and Miller, 1958). If these conditions are met, a change in the capital structure either increases or decreases the profitability of the firm. It was the use of debt instruments in the formation of the capital structure that gave the firm a competitive advantage over others.

Jensen and Meckling (1976) analyzed and highlighted another aspect: how the use of debt increases the profitability or competitiveness of the firm. Using borrowed funds as a source of funding, the tunneling work was stopped, which lowered agency costs and reduced conflicts. The firm's non-tunneling management provided a competitive edge. Miller (1977) highlighted another aspect by mentioning the compromise point of view. The explanation indicated that the first priority was to take advantage of tax protection for this debt. The higher the debt, the more tax breaks for the firm. However, debt comes with a cost to use the debt. The study made a very clear statement that debt gave the firm a competitive advantage as long as the cost of the debt was not less than the tax incentives it received.

Myers and Mailuf (1984) extended this work and emphasized the hierarchy perspective. Deciding how to finance the firm. First of all, it is necessary to use domestic financing, which is considered the cheapest source. If further financing is required, debt financing must be used. If the firm still needs additional funding, then move on to equity financing, but the costs associated with equity financing have been enormous.

From the above perspectives, the cryptic nature of debt has been clarified. It seems that the competitiveness of the company has both increased and decreased depending on usability. Similar results have been obtained by the various studies mentioned below, and their explanations have been covered in the approaches defined above. Lorenzoni and Lipparini (1999) confirmed the positive impact of debt on firm competitiveness. A similar result was confirmed by Lixin and Lin (2008). Campello (2006) confirmed the decline in firm competitiveness after use of debt.

Liquidity

Brealey et al. (2006) highlighted the problem of liquidity, pointing out that “determining the cost of liquidity was one of ten outstanding financing issues”. The firm's ability to effectively meet its short-term financial needs without selling the asset at a large discount is indicative of a good liquidity position. The financial crisis in the United States has shown the importance of liquidity to the firm. The question arose as to why a firm would hold liquid assets and how this liquidity helps to gain a competitive advantage. Hicks (1936) emphasized that this was due to the firm's uncertainty about having to hold liquid assets to meet any short-term requirements that, if unresolved, would reduce overall profitability. This was a warning motive for holding liquid assets. Jensen (1986) emphasized the management motive for holding liquid assets. As management wanted to maximize shareholder wealth, various profitable investments were made to do so. For a successful completion, the firm needs to maintain a better liquidity position, otherwise the liquidity crisis increases the solvency risk clearly evident during the US crisis (Burja, 2011). Foley et al. (2007) identified another motive for holding liquid assets. A firm without cash required at the time of tax payment had to liquidate its liquid assets to pay tax. This has been called the liquidity tax perspective. Various studies have been conducted to examine the effect of liquidity position on a firm's profitability. Kim et al. (1998) examined the effect of liquidity on the competitiveness of US firms and found a positive relationship. US companies face liquidity risk due to the fact that they paid less attention to liquid assets, so firms must maintain an optimal level of liquidity. If firms had better liquidity, that would be a competitive advantage over others. Liquidity risk reduced a firm's profitability and halted capital mobilization, confirmed by Dedu (2003).

The management approach confirmed that the firm's management improved the firm's competitiveness by increasing liquidity (Muhammad and Haider (2011)). Similar results were observed in Gill and Matur (2011) after studying Canadian service firms, and Koranke and Adarkua (2013) after studying the Ghanaian market. Philbeck and Krueger (2005) conducted a study involving 970 firms in 26 different sectors. The result showed a negative impact of liquidity on competitiveness. These results were confirmed by Juan García-Teruel and Martínez-Solano (2007).

Production asset

The increase in the number of manufacturing assets acquired by the firm proved to be a source of competitiveness. These assets increased the productivity of the firm, which ultimately reduced the unit cost, which gave a competitive advantage over others in selling quality products at lower prices. Production assets are used to obtain cheap secured loans. Liquid assets cannot be used as collateral to raise secured funds due to discounted risk (Liu and Hung, 2006).

In underdeveloped countries, technical capacity was inadequate, so a higher share of productive assets led to high depreciation costs, wasted use and reduced competitiveness (Deloof, 2003). Liargovas and Skandalis (2010) studied 102 firms listed on the Athens Stock Exchange from 1997 to 2004 and confirmed that firms are inefficient in the use of fixed assets, thus reducing the firm's competitiveness. Romanian chemical companies also showed similar results, confirmed by Burja (2011). Okwo et al. (2012) confirmed that bureaucracy is the main reason for the inefficient use of production assets.

Firm size

The high-volume firm was large in size, giving it a competitive advantage over smaller firms because they had the potential to improve productivity. Thanks to high productivity, firms have achieved economies of scale as well as economies of scale. Over time, firms have developed various methods for the correct and efficient use of assets. Hymer and Pashigian (1962) conducted research to confirm the relationship between the size of American firms and their efficiency. Manufacturing companies were selected for the study, which showed a negative relationship between the desired variables.

Shepherd (1972) and Leibenstein (1976) also confirmed a similar relationship and explained the reason for the negative relationship, which was associated with huge investments in plant assets with a less skilled worker who could manage and use these assets. The firm took an interest in training and human resource development in order to turn negative relationships into positive ones in the future. Majumdar (1997) confirmed a positive relationship after a study of 1,020 Indian firms. These firms have developed a standard operating procedure for the efficient use of a large asset base. It also allowed the firm to achieve economies of scale and economies of scale (Punnose, 2008).

Investments

Investment, defined as a strategy to diversify a firm's risk by investing in shares of other firms over a period of time, which helped the firm to reduce liquidity and solvency risks and also contributed to the flow of income (Lev and Tiagarajan 1993). However, Abarbanell and Bushey (1997) found a negative relationship between investment and firm competitiveness. The reason

was that the firm did not identify appropriate sources for investment, resulting in the value of the investment being greater than the return on investment.

Beneish et al. (2001) and Fairfield et al. (2003) confirmed a negative relationship between investment and competitiveness. He further explained the reason that management had internal and external conflicts that led to unproductive investments, due to which the firm lost its competitive advantage. However, Lee (2004) has provided a more detailed reason for this negative relationship after studying large American firms for over 40 years. Weak regulations were a major loophole in which the firm's management got involved in tunneling, with the result that higher investment reduced competitiveness. Countries with improved legislation reap investment benefits that give the firm a competitive advantage over other firms. Investments in technology companies have increased the competitiveness of healthcare companies (Thouin et al., 2008). The result was confirmed by Rakotomavo (2012).

Export

The reason for choosing exports as one of the factors of the firm's competitiveness, since Girma et al. (2004) confirmed that a domestic firm gained a competitive advantage by exporting over non-exporting firms. Exports have helped improve product quality by meeting international quality standards, and have helped the firm take advantage of economies of scale and economies of scale. Bausch and Christ (2007) confirmed a positive relationship between exports and firm competitiveness after conducting a meta-analysis. Access to large markets increased sales, forcing the firm to increase productivity, resulting in economies of scale and scale, as explained by Girma et al. (2004).

Bernard et al. (2007) conducted a comparative study between US exporting and non-exporting companies. The result confirmed the view put forward by Girma et al. (2004). Mayer and Ottaviano (2007) confirmed positive relationships in European companies. However, Grazzi (2012) performed regression and nonparametric tests that did not show any significant relationship. Temouri et al. (2013) also showed a similar result for UK firms, as explained by Grazzi (2012). The high value of exports diminishes benefits, which are the main reason for negative attitudes towards competitiveness. There were many export conditions in the UK that made the exporting companies less competitive.

Market share

A firm is considered successful if the income statement shows strong sales. These high sales are not only a source of income for the business, but also an indicator of the firm's market share. Higher sales mean more market share. A firm with a large market share had to increase productivity through economies of scale and economies of scale, which lowered the firm's production costs and increased profitability, as well as gave a competitive advantage, which made market share a competitive factor (Gale, 1972).

Shepherd (1972) found a positive relationship between market share and firm competitiveness. Jacobson and Aaker (1985) confirmed the result of Shepherd (1972) and the rationale for such a relationship given by Gale (1972). Ailawadi et al. (1999) conducted a study using structural equation modeling of percent change in profitability over six years. The positive relationship was confirmed. The result showed that the unit cost of acquiring a high market share declined with increasing productivity, as already explained by Gale (1972).

The data was collected from a survey of 20 textile companies using data from 2015 to 2020.

Independent financial factors

1. Leverage: The ratio of total debt to total equity was used, which showed how many times debt financing was provided versus equity financing.
2. Production assets: the ratio of the total amount of fixed assets to the total amount of assets was used, which provided the percentage of production assets in the total structure of assets.
3. Liquidity: the ratio of current assets to current liabilities was used, which showed how many times the firm was able to pay the most current financial liability.
4. Investment: The ratio of total investment to total assets was used, which described the percentage of investment in total assets that helped the firm solve liquidity problems and also provided an income stream.
5. Firm size: The logarithm of total assets reveals the size of the firm's business. A higher value means that the firm had a larger asset base, which was indicative of large business transactions conducted by the firm.

Independent non-financial factor

1. Market share: The logarithm of net total sales reflects the market information obtained by the firm. Higher value means that the firm has more market share than its competitors.
2. Export: A dummy variable was used for export. One for an exporting firm and zero for a non-exporting firm.
3. Use of ICT: This variable refers to how companies use information technology in manufacturing. Measured by survey results on a Likert scale of 1 to 7.

Dependent variable

Return on Assets: The ratio of net income before tax to total assets was used to provide information on how efficiently the firm was using total assets and return on assets. The value of this coefficient showed the firm's profitability as an indicator of competitiveness.

Regression Model

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FinLev + \beta_2 ProAsset + \beta_3 Liquidity + \beta_4 Inv + \beta_5 FirmSize + \beta_6 MarShare + \beta_7 Exporting + \beta_8 ITUsage$$

An econometric analysis of the competitiveness of enterprises in the textile industry using IT is analyzed using a regression model. These are Amu Darya Textile, Kuvatekstil, Art Soft Tex, Nortex style. Their data was taken from financial statements from 2017 to 2020. IT use was obtained through a survey. The results will be presented below.

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Return on assets	16	0.385	0.0794145	0.27	0.51
Financial leverage	16	0.601875	0.0943199	0.45	0.8
Production asset	16	0.61	0.0832666	0.44	0.72

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Liquidity	16	1.119375	0.3537507	0.6	1.74
Investments	16	0.578125	0.120345	0.3	0.78
Firm size	16	7.463125	0.621908	6.1	8.3
Market share	16	7.82375	1.518139	5.1	9.4
Export	16	0.4375	0.5123475	0	1
Use of ICT	16	6.25	0.7745967	5	7

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics show that the regression uses 16 observations, this analysis uses linear regression. The data shows that all values are different, this table shows the mean values of the observations, standard deviations, and the minimum and maximum values of each observation, the reason for the analysis is to display the general information of the observations.

	Return on assets	Financial leverage	Production asset	Liquidity	Investments	Firm size	Market share	Export	Use of ICT
Return on assets	1								
Financial leverage	0.6448	1							
Production asset	0.3196	0.0543	1						
Liquidity	-0.3371	-0.7287	0.1729	1					
Investments	0.4719	-0.0308	-0.1038	0.02	1				
Firm size	0.5246	0.4193	0.5889	-0.111	0.2118	1			
Market share	0.3627	-0.002	0.7676	0.3036	0.0959	0.7988	1		
Export	0.0573	0.0095	-0.0469	0.0568	0.2088	-0.2033	-0.1702	1	
Use of ICT	0.2168	0.2395	-0.124	-0.3668	0.0626	-0.1124	-0.311	-0.462	1

Table 2: Correlation matrix

The key goal of regression analysis is to isolate the relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable. The interpretation of the regression coefficient is that it is the average change in the dependent variable for each unit of change in the independent variable when all other explanatory variables remain constant. This last part is critical to our discussion of multicollinearity. There is no multicollinearity here.

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	(1)	(2)	3
VARIABLES	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Financial leverage	1.031***	0.970***	1.047***
	(0.268)	(0.155)	(0.260)
Production asset	0.114	0.112	
	(0.156)	(0.146)	
Liquidity	0.0140		0.0132
	(0.0483)		(0.0469)
Investments	0.228**	0.218**	0.216**
	(0.0905)	(0.0777)	(0.0864)
Firm size	-0.132**	-0.125**	-0.136**
	(0.0528)	(0.0441)	(0.0509)
Market share	0.0541**	0.0531**	0.0605***
	(0.0180)	(0.0166)	(0.0153)
Export	-0.0360*	-0.0342*	-0.0338*
	(0.0178)	(0.0157)	(0.0170)
Use of ICT	0.0262*	0.0241**	0.0271**
	(0.0112)	(0.00796)	(0.0108)
Constant	0.0141	0.0386	0.0581
	(0.162)	(0.129)	(0.145)
Observations	16	16	16
R-squared	0.921	0.920	0.915
Standard errors in parentheses			
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1			

Table: Regression Results

The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of the regression:

Leverage is statistically significant for ROA because the t value of this variable is 2.49 and it is significant in all models. An increase in leverage by 1 unit will increase ROA by 1 percent. Investment also has a statistically significant positive value across all models. A 1 percent increase in the investment amount will increase ROA by about 0.22 percent. However, firm size has a negative relationship with ROA, which can be explained by the fact that larger firms have lower ROA. If a company has a large market share, they also have a higher ROA. The export potential of the company has a negative relationship with the return on assets, this can be explained by the fact that exports are either more expensive, or they will export at lower prices in order to enter the world market. ICTs have a positive relationship with companies' return on

investment, which means that if companies increase their use of ICTs, their return on investment ratios increase.

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